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FORMS OF INTERNATIONAL COOPERATION IN CRIMINAL ACTIVITY

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Abstract: this article identifies the main forms of international cooperation in criminal cases. Also, specific features of international cooperation in criminal cases are studied and justified by statistical data. Opinions of local and foreign scientists on the classification of forms of international cooperation in criminal cases were studied and conclusions were given.

Key words: crime, international cooperation, legal assistance, extradition, criminal prosecution, procedural action, extradition, prosecution.

INTRODUCTION

The scope, main directions and forms of cooperation in criminal cases are determined by the content and characteristics of international and domestic crimes, as well as the development of the policy and legal system of various countries and the level of their participation in international relations.

The main forms of international cooperation in criminal cases include: 1) implementation of requests for legal assistance in connection with the implementation of certain procedural actions; 2) criminal prosecution; 3) extradition of a person for criminal prosecution or execution of sentence.

The legal basis for implementing legal aid requests is the instructions of foreign legal institutions. Legal assistance includes a whole set of elements regulated by international and national jurisprudence (order of interaction of law enforcement agencies, order details, order execution order, etc.).

It should be noted that in accordance with the Code of Criminal Procedure of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the court, prosecutor, investigator, and investigator

executes the request to perform procedural actions assigned to them in accordance with the established procedure, received from the relevant competent body of a foreign country, in accordance with the international agreements of the Republic of Uzbekistan or on the basis of the principle of reciprocity[2, 360].

One of the forms of international cooperation in criminal cases is criminal prosecution. The importance of this type of cooperation in criminal cases cannot be overestimated, because criminal prosecution is an activity limited by the constitutional rights of citizens, and its results, as a rule, have serious consequences for specific individuals. Legal assistance agreements contain a provision that each state, at the request of the other state, will initiate criminal proceedings under its own law against its citizens who are suspected of committing a crime on the territory of another state. At the same time, criminal prosecution in the requested country can be carried out only if the act is also considered criminal in this country [3, 2].

The need to resolve issues related to criminal prosecution arises in cases where the accused person hides in another country after committing a crime and his extradition is requested, as well as in cases where extradition is refused. In this case, the country of citizenship of such a person acts as the initiator of criminal prosecution. However, without the written consent of the foreign country whose citizen has entered the jurisdiction, the country of which he is a citizen is not allowed to prosecute a non-extradited person independently.

It should be noted that the transfer of criminal prosecution differs from international legal assistance, as well as from the extradition of persons, in terms of the purpose of the transfer and the procedure for the transfer of legal consequences. Thus, when international legal assistance is provided, a criminal case is initiated, investigated and considered on its merits in a country in need of assistance. The final decision is taken on behalf of the same state. The results of international legal assistance have no independent value except in criminal cases.

All reports on the issues of criminal prosecution are carried out through the central authorities of the countries specified in the relevant international agreements

and domestic legislation. The General Prosecutor's Office is such a central body in the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Our studies have shown that in accordance with Article 599 of the Code of Criminal Procedure of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2022, the Investigation Department of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan will detain citizens who have committed a crime and are in the territory of a foreign country for criminal prosecution. 468 applications were submitted. At the same time, in accordance with Article 601, 390 applications were received from the law enforcement agencies of foreign countries regarding the extradition of persons who committed crimes on the territory of foreign countries for prosecution.

Thus, during the months of January-August 2023, the Investigative Department of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan sent 374 applications to the competent authorities of foreign countries to prosecute foreign citizens who committed crimes on the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan. At the same time, 354 instructions were received from the competent authorities of foreign countries on the prosecution of citizens of the Republic of Uzbekistan who committed crimes on the territory of foreign countries [4, 3].

In accordance with the agreements on providing legal assistance for the implementation of criminal prosecution, the central authorities of the states can receive both the initiated criminal case and the materials of criminal prosecution. If a criminal case has been initiated by the requested country, the investigation of this case will be continued by the requested country in accordance with its domestic legislation. Before issuing an arrest warrant, it is necessary to carry out an appropriate number of investigative actions confirming the legality of the criminal prosecution in this country and the possibility of its continuation in the country of which the accused is a citizen, as well as to conduct appropriate investigative actions regarding the extension of the investigation, the detention of the accused and the resumption of the case.

Interaction is impossible without a mutual understanding of the essence of the issues to be resolved jointly and the consent of the parties on the subject, procedures and consequences of such interaction. The real essence of interaction lies in mutual assistance and support of the cooperating parties [6].

Summarizing the above, we can say that the grounds for sending a request for criminal prosecution are the presence of the following conditions:

- 1) the person who committed the crime must have the citizenship of the Republic of Uzbekistan;
- 2) the crime must have been committed by him in the territory of a foreign country;
- 3) the person who committed the crime must have returned to the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

On the basis of these conditions, the issue of criminal prosecution by Uzbekistan can be considered.

One of the important components of international cooperation in criminal cases is the extradition of persons.

Extradition (eng., fr. extradition) is the practice of handing over a citizen or a foreign citizen from one country to another foreign country[1,547].

Extradition means the procedure of bringing a person accused of committing a crime or a person convicted by the country where this person is located to another country for prosecution or execution of the sentence. The institution of extradition is a practice of cooperation between countries in the field of criminal procedure at the international level. In this lies the issue of ensuring the inevitability of responsibility and punishment of every person who commits a crime.

Extradition is a complex legal process. It cannot be implemented without reference to separate legal documents, constitution, criminal and criminal procedural codes. Because human rights are considered a first-class value, and this is reflected in the norms of national legislation. For example, the procedure for extradition and its grounds are based on constitutional norms.

The issue of extradition in the Republic of Uzbekistan is resolved on the basis of normative legal documents developed in accordance with the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, as well as international agreements, conventions, agreements signed with foreign countries on this issue.

Articles 599-609 of the Criminal Procedure Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan refer to sending a request for the extradition of a person who is in the territory of a foreign country, the scope of criminal responsibility of a person who has been extradited to the Republic of Uzbekistan, sending a request, extradition of a person who is in the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan to a foreign country and refusing to extradite, withholding the issues of arrest and detention, the procedures for handing over a detained person in transit are covered [2, 443].

In the cases provided for by the laws and international agreements of the Republic of Uzbekistan and in accordance with the procedure or on the basis of the principle of reciprocity, the General Prosecutor's Office of the Republic of Uzbekistan may send a request to the competent body of a foreign country to bring a person who is in the territory of a foreign country to criminal responsibility or hand over for the execution of a sentence.

Extradition relates to the detention of the extradited person. Therefore, it always affects not only the sovereignty and interests of the state, but also the basic rights and freedoms of a person. From this point of view, extradition is one of the main types of international cooperation in criminal cases and its implementation is a complex process.

Relations between states on extradition issues are regulated by the following legal documents:

- International conventions and agreements on legal assistance (Minsk Convention of 1993, Chisinau Convention of 2001), which provide for the possibility of extradition of persons who have committed crimes in the manner and conditions determined by the parties to the agreement;

- the national legislation of the states is expressed, that is, articles 599-609 of the Criminal Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan determine the general rules of unilateral extradition, as well as specify the authorized institution or officials who resolve issues related to extradition.

According to V. M. Volzhenkina, granting extradition request is a discretionary decision of one state in relation to another state, taking into account the mutual provision of this type of legal assistance[5, 137].

In the Republic of Uzbekistan, the body authorized to consider extradition issues is the General Prosecutor's Office. A request to prosecute or detain a person in the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan for the execution of a sentence is considered by the General Prosecutor's Office of the Republic of Uzbekistan in accordance with the international agreements of the Republic of Uzbekistan or on the basis of the principle of reciprocity [2, 299].

Principle of Reciprocity In a similar situation, the competent body of a foreign state, which sent a request for the extradition of a person in the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan, It is confirmed by a written promise that the extradition of the person will be carried out at the request of the authorized body. The decision to extradite a person in the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan is made by the Prosecutor General of the Republic of Uzbekistan or his deputy. When there is a request from several countries to extradite the same person, the decision to which country to extradite the person is made by the Prosecutor General of the Republic of Uzbekistan [2, 366].

Investigative bodies do not make direct decisions on extradition. Their tasks in fulfilling the request for extradition are to carry out actions related to arrest (if this is assigned to investigative bodies), to decide on the issues of extending the period of detention, to conduct a psychiatric examination of extradited persons), to provide a person with a defender, to conduct "hearing" events of investigative actions. (for example, forensic examination) is limited to.

METHODS

The fact that the extradition of criminals is one of the acts of providing legal aid and this process is carried out on the basis of special agreements (relying on national norms), decided and regulated between competent bodies and officials. It can be seen that extradition is not a one-time action, but a process consisting of whole sequences.

A.Kh. Saidov defined the concept of extradition as one of the types of legal assistance in criminal cases carried out in the international cooperation of states. Extradition is defined as the transfer by a state of a person in its territory to another state for criminal prosecution or execution of a sentence[7, 228].

R.A.Sayfulov conducted a special research on this issue and concluded that the extradition of a person should be regulated not only by international law, but also by national criminal procedural legislation, which is also proven in the history and development of this institution. The institution of extradition is fundamentally different from expulsion, declaring a person "persona non grata", repatriation (returning to the country) and transfer of a person under the terms of the International Tribunal. It covers international-legal and criminal-procedural procedures [8, 9-10].

D.Sh. Umarchonova defines extradition as "handover of a person accused or convicted of a crime by one country to another country in accordance with the procedure established in international treaties and agreements for the purpose of trial and execution of the sentence"[9, 27].

In our opinion, extradition refers to the procedure of handing over and handing over a person found guilty or convicted of a crime to another country for prosecution or execution of a sentence. Extradition ensures cooperation in the fight against crime and serves to achieve the goal of the criminal process, to restore broken legal relations, to maintain the standards of equality and justice in society.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

According to statistics, in 2022, the Investigation Department under the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan received 390 extradition

materials, 231 of which were allowed to be extradited, and 59 were rejected. The Investigative Department under the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan sent 468 requests for extradition to the competent authorities of foreign countries, 309 of them were satisfied during the period under review, and 159 were rejected[4, 2].

At the same time, during 6 months of 2023, the Investigative Department of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan received 354 materials on the extradition of persons from Uzbekistan, of which 343 were approved. The Investigative Department under the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan sent 374 requests for extradition to the competent authorities of foreign countries, 260 of which were granted during the period under consideration, and 14 were refused extradition [4, 3].

CONCLUSION

In short, it is appropriate to determine the size, main forms and directions of international cooperation in criminal matters. Through this, we will achieve a theoretical solution to the existing problems in the field. It also serves to determine the procedural status of the participants of the process by fully classifying the subjects of cooperation in criminal cases.

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